

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

GQSAR, PHARMACOPHORE MAPPING AND MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES OF SOME PYRIDAZINONE DERIVATIVES.

Rakesh Panda^{*}, Monica Kachroo, Lokesh Pathak

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Al-Ameen College of Pharmacy, Bangalore.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 06/04/2017

Available online

09/06/2018

Keywords

Pyridazinones,
GQSAR,
Pharmacophore Matching,
Molecular Docking,
Inverse Target Screening.

ABSTRACT

Various literatures are reported on the versatility of pyridazinone molecules, an article was selected with reported IC₅₀. 20 compounds (S1-S20) were selected for combined and stepwise *in silico* studies on pyridazinone moieties in the form of GQSAR, pharmacophore matching and molecular docking studies. These studies revealed important physicochemical properties of pyridazinones responsible for various biological activities. Group based QSAR (GQSAR) on COX-2 was carried out and 2 best models were studied. Pharm Mapper webserver was used for *in silico* reverse target screening to find out potential therapeutic targets for pyridazinones. The targets identified using *in-silico* method like Tyrosine phosphatases (PDB ID- 1NWL), Sorbitol dehydrogenase (PDB ID- 1PL6), Cell division protein kinase 2 (PDB ID - 2B54), Mitogen activated protein kinase 14 (PDB ID-2ZB1), Glucocorticoid receptor (PDB ID- 3CLD) were further screened by molecular docking approach to find best target among these. Docking scores and interactions of pyridazinones revealed Mitogen activated protein kinase 14 as its putative target. MAP 14 kinase is already a well known anti-inflammatory mediator receptor protein hence this *in silico* study and the data generated have proved that the molecules having pyridazinone moiety could be developed as anti-inflammatory lead compounds.

Corresponding author

Mr Rakesh Panda

Lecturer,

Department of pharmaceutical chemistry,

Al-Ameen College of Pharmacy,

Hosur Road, Bangalore -

rakeshpanda555@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Mr Rakesh Panda et al.** GQSAR, Pharmacophore Mapping and Molecular Docking Studies of Some Pyridazinone Derivatives. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(05).

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

www.iajpr.com

INTRODUCTION

Various computational approaches to search the lead molecules have been widely used to accelerate the drug discovery process. Some of these approaches include Hansch method, Free-Wilson method and conventional 2-D /3-DQSAR methods. Among these, a new Fragment-based/Group-based QSAR (G-QSAR) methodology has shown promising outcomes in ongoing drug discovery studies and lead optimization efforts. This method provides models with predictive ability similar or better to conventional methods and in addition provides hints for sites of chemical modifications of the pharmacophore in the parent molecule. G-QSAR provides descriptor evaluation only for the substituent groups or molecular fragments rather than for whole molecule. In addition, cross terms are calculated from product of descriptors at different substituent sites or fragments and used as descriptors to improve the QSAR models. The descriptor range for substituents or fragments are used to search for new groups or fragments; respectively leading to design of novel molecules with improved activity and / or physicochemical properties. G-QSAR developed models provide hints about the impact of each fragment on variation in biological activity. Thus, the interpretation of G-QSAR models to develop new molecules is a more practical and achievable task compared to 2D and 3D QSARs [1].

Drug target identification, which includes many distinct algorithms for finding genes and proteins, is the first step in drug discovery. When 3D structures of the targets are available, the problem of target identification is usually converted to finding the best interaction mode between the potential target candidates and probe small molecules. Pharmacophore, which is the spatial arrangement of features that is essential for a molecule to interact with a specific target receptor, is an alternative method despite of molecular docking for achieving this goal [2].

The molecular docking approach can be used to model the interaction between a small molecule and a protein at the atomic level, which allow us to characterize the behavior of small molecules in the binding site of target proteins as well as to elucidate fundamental biochemical processes. The docking process involves two basic steps: prediction of the ligand conformation as well as its position and orientation within these sites (usually referred to as pose) and assessment of the binding affinity [3].

Pyridazin-3-one, an unsaturated form of pyridazine with carbonyl group on third carbon, has been considered as a magic moiety (wonder nucleus) which posses almost all types of biological activities. This diversity in the biological response profile has attracted the attention of many researchers to explore this skeleton to its multiple potential against several activities [4].

Correlation between the *in silico* findings with the *in vitro* studies is another very important task which is necessary to prove the activity and potency of the molecules. This part of research work has main objective to find out the best target for the molecules and to define the group fragment which is actually defining the activity of the molecule. Present study is focused on the designing of therapeutically active pyridazinone molecules and searching the most suitable binding receptors for the pyridazinone molecules.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

GQSAR

From the various literatures reported on pyridazinones, an article [5] was selected with reported IC₅₀. 20 compounds (S1-S20) were selected for G-QSAR studies. IC₅₀ values were converted to pIC₅₀ values and along with structures were subjected for G-QSAR studies, targeting selective COX-2 receptor by using various descriptors. G-QSAR modelling was executed using molecular design suit (vLife MDS software package [6], version 4.4) on windows 7 ultimate operating system, with Intel core i5 processor.

Selection of training and test set:

Training and test set data selection were done by using Sphere Exclusion method. In this the variance cut off limit was set to 4, so that out of 20 molecules, 6 molecules will be in test set and 20 molecules will be training set. Following are the training and test set molecules.

Training set molecules (Table 1)

Test set molecules (Table 2).

Calculation of descriptors:

Physicochemical, interaction dependent and alignment independent descriptors were calculated for all 20 molecules. After descriptor calculation invariable columns were deleted.

Model building:

Variable selection was performed by using Partial Least Square regression, principle component regression, multiple linear regression and k nearest neighbour (kNN) method and adapting following selection methods 1) forward backward selection method 2) forward method 3) Genetic algorithm 4) simulated annealing method. Several trial and error runs were performed and the models with optimum values for regression coefficient and other statistical parameters were taken into consideration. For every trial, cross correlation limit was set to 0.8. Number of allowed variables in final equations was set to 03. Term selection criteria were kept as squared correlation coefficient (r^2) whereas for k nearest neighbour (kNN) based methods it was cross validated squared correlation coefficient (q^2). Variance limit was set to 0.1. Number of cross validation was set to 14. After several iterations for model building, best two models were selected for analysis.

PHARMACOPHORE MATCHING

In order to hunt for best protein receptor targets for 20 pyridazinone (S1-S20) molecules reported in literature, pharmacophore matching algorithm was implemented in pharmmapper web server [2]. After implementation of the algorithm, various protein receptor targets exhibiting highest \bar{z} score were selected from top 10 screened pharmacophore models.

MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES

Molecular docking studies were carried out on 5 distinct protein receptor targets which were previously selected from pharmacophore matching algorithms using autodock vina software tool [7].

Protein preparation:

Protein preparation was done in 'Discovery studio 4.5.0 visualiser'. Proteins were prepared by deleting water molecules and by adding polar hydrogens to the 3D X ray crystallographic structure of the protein receptor target. Co-ordinates of co crystallised ligands were separately saved for definition of active site.

Ligand preparation:

All ligands were prepared in vlfe engine software version 4.4, employing Merck Molecular Force field (MMFF) optimization method with 10,000 number of cycles and convergence criteria of 0.01Å. Distance dependent dielectric properties were employed for charge calculations.

'Autodock vina' algorithm was run and top 10 poses of each ligand for respective protein receptor targets were saved and analyzed for their binding affinity (kcal/mol) and ligand protein interactions (electrostatic and van der Waals interactions)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

QSAR STUDIES

With regard to QSAR modeling, our first goal was to establish a predictive model with a reasonable number of input features to ensure good generalization performance. While correlating various descriptors, biological activity is the most important means to study structure–activity relationships, the interest lies in deciding when to stop adding a new descriptor to the model. Thus, the optimal model should use the minimum number of descriptors to obtain the best fit. To achieve this, a well accepted method is to find out the saturation point, a point beyond which there is no considerable improvement in the regression coefficient (r^2 and q^2) values even if a new descriptor is added. MLR, PCR, PLS and kNN techniques were used in the present study for selecting a significant set of descriptors in order to build the significant models. In this section, the prediction performances of the method proposed by four different models (MLR, PCR, PLS and kNN) were evaluated. The MLR, PCR, PLS and kNN models predicted the training data with a r^2 of 0.8234, 0.8238, 0.8213, 0.8120, 0.8317 and 0.7590 together with q^2 estimating to 0.7363, 0.5246, 0.7406, 0.7497, 0.6317, 0.5006, 0.6146, 0.6159 and 0.7376 respectively.

Out of all nine models, model 3 and model 8 appeared to be the best QSAR model obtained by the Principle Component Regression (PCR) and kappa Nearest Neighbour (kNN) analysis method. In this study we have limited the number of presented equations to the best 2 regression models of the whole set. The actual and predicted activities of Model 3 and Model 8 are compared in the Table 3.

Table 3:- Actual and predicted activities of Model 3 and Model 8.

TRAINING SET			
Molecules	Actual Activity	Model 3 Predicted Activity	Model 8 Predicted Activity
S16	7.045	6.94051	6.432
S9	6.387	6.42686	6.37683
S12	6.387	6.42686	6.37683
S6	5.886	5.25615	5.13933
S3	4.95	5.25615	5.45133
S4	5.32	5.25615	5.328
S10	5.148	5.25615	5.38533
S20	5.229	5.70127	5.66333
S15	5.958	5.81103	5.77564
S18	5.769	5.81103	5.95642
S19	6.443	6.37835	5.92401
S8	6.522	6.42686	6.31361
S14	6.455	6.26864	6.36596
S17	6.045	6.32798	6.36858
TEST SET			
S11	5.229	6.42686	6.432
S1	4.481	5.25615	5.13933
S2	4.67	5.25615	5.13933
S5	4.481	5.25615	5.13933
S13	4.481	5.25615	5.13933
S7	5.148	5.25615	5.13933

The contribution plots and the fitness plots (calculated versus observed values) of the model 3 and model 8 are shown in Figs. 1–3.

Figure 1:- Contribution plot for Model 3.

Figure 2:- Fitness Plot for Model 3.

Figure 3:- Fitness plot for Model 8.

Equation for Model 3:

$$0.1891 \times R1\text{-}4\text{PathClusterCount} + 0.3023 \times R1\text{-}T_2_F_2 - 0.046 \times R1\text{-}SaaCHE\text{-index} + 5.8110$$

Equation for Model 3 shows the positive contribution of R1-4PathClusterCount (40%) (This is the count of total number of four bond paths in a molecule), R1-T₂F₂ (35%) (This descriptor signifies total number of double bonded atoms separated from fluorine by 2 bonds distance) and negative contribution of R1-SaaCHE-index (26%) (This is electrotopological index of total number of carbon atoms connected to the hydrogen along with two aromatic bonds). This model exhibits importance of fluorine as a substituent not only in terms of its presence but also its spacing from pyridazinone ring by distance equivalent to 2 bonds.

Model 8 shows that descriptors involved in the model (R1-4PathClusterCount, R1-T₂F₂ and R1-T_CC₁) contribute positively for the activity as their descriptor range values are positive. Descriptor R1-T_CC₁ indicates the count of number of carbon atoms separated from any carbon atom by 1 bond distance in the molecule. This model indicates that in a molecule carbon-carbon bond linkage is more favorable instead of any inclusion of any hetero atoms in between two carbon atoms.

PHARMACOPHORE MAPPING:

The pyridazinone compounds taken for the present study were as shown in table 1 and table 2. Molecule S 18 was submitted to Pharm Mapper web server. Nearly 300 targets were generated with multiple PDB entries. Inverse screening was then performed to find out 10 most potential targets with their PDB ID and z score. From this one can infer that pyridazinone molecule can be active on several prominent receptor proteins. Among these, Tyrosine phosphatases (PDB ID- 1NWL), Sorbitol dehydrogenase (PDB ID- 1PL6), Cell division protein kinase 2 (PDB ID - 2B54), Mitogen activated protein kinase 14 (PDB ID-2ZB1), Glucocorticoid receptor (PDB ID- 3CLD) can be considered as prominent targets, as these show highest z score.

Table 4:- Desired pharmacophore models.

Rank	PDB ID	Target Name	Number of Feature ↑	Fit Score ↑	Normalized Fit Score ↑	z'-score ↑
1	1PL6	Sorbitol dehydrogenase	5	4.064	0.8128	3.07794
2	1IF9	Carbonic anhydrase 2	5	3.892	0.7783	2.75922
3	1YZ3	Phenylethanolamine N-methyltransferase	11	4.213	0.383	2.49551
4	1TG2	Phenylalanine-4-hydroxylase	5	3.691	0.7382	2.06426
5	1LZI	Histo-blood group ABO system transferase	7	3.746	0.5351	2.06376
6	3CLD	Glucocorticoid receptor	8	3.833	0.4791	1.88139
7	2B54	Cell division protein kinase 2	8	3.753	0.4691	1.857
8	2ZB1	Mitogen-activated protein kinase 14	7	3.833	0.5476	1.75559
9	1NWL	Tyrosine-protein phosphatase non-receptor type 1	8	3.731	0.4663	1.73794
10	1Y8Y	Cell division protein kinase 2	7	3.806	0.5438	1.56292

The pharmacophore models of all top 10 targets and fitting of ligand to these models are represented in table 5.

Table 5:- Molecule and pharmacophore models:

Hydrophobic Positive Negative Donor Acceptor Aromatic

MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES

Molecular docking studies were carried out on 5 distinct protein receptor targets which were previously selected from pharmacophore matching algorithms using autodock vina software tool.

All the compounds were docked upon each of the 5 desired receptor proteins and the best docked molecule with each of the receptor proteins along with their respective binding energy is listed in the table number 6.

Table 6:- Best docked molecule in each protein receptor.

PROTEIN NAME	COMPOUND CODE	BINDING ENERGY (Kcal/mol)
2B54 Cell Division protein kinase 2	 S14	-8.9
1PL6 Sorbitol Dehydrogenase	 S1	-8.7
3CLD Glucocorticoid receptor	 S1	-8.1
1NWL Tyrosine protein Phosphatase type 1	 S17	-7.7

CONCLUSION

Combined and stepwise *in silico* studies were carried out on pyridazinone moieties in the form of QSAR, Pharmacophore matching and Molecular docking studies. These studies revealed important physicochemical properties of pyridazinones responsible for various biological activities. Group based QSAR (GQSAR) on COX-2 was carried out and 2 best models were studied. It revealed the importance of electron withdrawing substituents on aromatic ring which is placed at 4th position of pyridazinone scaffold. In order to explore the potential therapeutic targets for pyridazinone moiety, *in silico* inverse target screening was done using Pharm Mapper web server. The targets identified using *in-silico* method like Tyrosine phosphatases (PDB ID- 1NWL), Sorbitol dehydrogenase (PDB ID- 1PL6), Cell division protein kinase 2 (PDB ID - 2B54), Mitogen activated protein kinase 14 (PDB ID-2ZB1), Glucocorticoid receptor (PDB ID- 3CLD) were further screened by molecular docking approach to find best target among these. Docking scores and interactions of pyridazinones revealed Mitogen activated protein kinase 14 as its putative target. MAP 14 kinase is already a well established anti-inflammatory mediator receptor protein hence this study emphasized that pyridazinones could be developed as anti-inflammatory lead compounds. Further, this study can will be extended to generation of new lead molecules and plotting a comparison between these *in silico* findings with the *in vitro/vivo* studies.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Authors are thankful to Advanced Research Wing of Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences, Bangalore for funding this research project. Authors are also thankful to Dr. Shobha Rani RH, Principal, Al-Ameen College of Pharmacy, for providing the facilities for conducting the research work.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All the authors of this research article have no conflict of interest.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- PLS – Partial Least Square regression.
- PCR – Principal Component regression.
- MLR – Multiple Linear regression.
- kNN – k Nearest Neighbour.

PDB – Protein Data Bank.

REFERENCE

1. Kale MA, Baheti KG G QSAR studies of novel 1,2,4-triazolo [3,4-b]- 1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives. *Der Pharm Sin*, 2015;6(9): 15-20.
2. Liu X, Ouyang S, Yu B, Huang K, Liu Y, Gong J et al. PharmMapper Server: a web server for potential drug target identification via pharmacophore mapping approach. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 2010,38, W609-W614.
3. Meng XY, Zhang HX, Mezei M, Cui M. Molecular docking: A powerful approach for structure based drug discovery. *Curr Comput Aided Drug Des*. 2011, June1;7(2):146-157.
4. Asif Md, Singh Anita. Exploring potential, synthetic methods and general chemistry of pyridazine and pyridazinone : A brief introduction. *Int J Chem Tech Res*. 2010;2(2):1112-28.
5. Khokara SL, Seth S, Garg SS. Molecular docking studies on 2-substituted-6(4-methylphenyl)-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones,3-substituted-6(4-methylphenyl)-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones and Pyridazin substituted triazin. *Int J Curr Res*, 2014;6(11): 9745-9759.
6. Ajmani S, Jadav K, Kulkarni SA. Group based QSAR (G-QSAR): mitigating interpretation challenges in QSAR. *QSAR Comb Sci*.2009;28(1):36-51.
7. Trott O, Olson AJ. Autodock Vina: Improving the speed and accuracy of docking with new scoring function, efficient optimisation and multi threading. *J Comp Chem*.2010; 31(2):455-461.
8. Li CS, Brideau C, Chan CC, Savoie C, Claveau D, Charleson S et al. Pyridazinones as selective cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitors. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*.2003; 13:597-600.
9. McCauley, J., Zivanovic, A. & Skropeta, D. Bioassays for anticancer activities. *Methods in Molecular Biology*, 2013, 1055: 191-205.
10. Miettinen M1, Rikala MS, Rys J, Lasota J, Wang ZF. Vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2 as a marker for malignant vascular tumors and mesothelioma: an immunohistochemical study of 262 vascular endothelial and 1640 nonvascular tumors. *Am J Surg Pathol*. 2012 Apr; 36(4):629-39.

54878478451180417

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

